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Assessment of Literacy and Numeracy in Early Childhood Education

A Review of the Literature

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Summary

- Assessment in early childhood is concerned with the processes of collecting information about children from various forms of evidence and then organising and interpreting that information to make judgements about children's development and learning (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021). It may be focused on individual children (Hussain, et al., 2019; Visser et al., 2012) but may also examine group work or pedagogical practice (Alasuutari et al., 2012). Assessment can be linked to two paradigms, which are referred to in various forms: positivist, developmental, standardised or prescribed, and sociocultural, learning-based or open. More contemporary approaches position assessment as democratic (Moss, 2011), participatory (Formosinho & Pascal, 2016) and moral practices (Buzzelli 2018).
- Standardised assessment provides information on how a child is developing in relation to others of the same age (Hussain 2019; Conti-Ramsden & Durkin, 2012). Standardised assessments are deemed essential in the area of special needs (Visser et al., 2012) as early detection of developmental problems enables the timely provision of supports for children and parents. However, standardised assessment has been strongly criticised (Auld 2019; Basford 2014; Brunsek 2017; Fundus 2015; Hussain 2019; Perlman 2016; Robert-Holmes 2017, 2019; Yoon 2015) as failing to engage with the wider social context of the child (Hussain 2019), and drawing on the discourse of readiness and achievement gaps, which mask issues of social and economic exclusion (Robert-Holmes 2017; Yoon 2015). Standardised instruments have also been criticised as not being sensitive enough (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin, 2012) to assess language in early childhood, particularly in relation to young children or children from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds (Verdon, et al., 2018).
- Established, informal assessments (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021; Alasuutarai et al., 2014; Carr & Lee, 2012) are integral and dynamic components of teaching and learning, and are characterised by collaboration between parents, early childhood professionals' and children (Ntuli 2014; Scull, 2021; Formosinho 2014). Literature cautions against the narrowing of assessment to specific skills (Pyle & DeLuca, 2017) and observation-based approaches offer opportunities for continual assessment that draws on multiple tools or formats (Gullo & Hughes, 2011; Wolfendale, 2000; Losardo & Notari Syverson, 2011; Picchio, 2014). These forms of assessment allow children themselves to make meaning of their learning experiences (Oliveira-Formosinho & Formosinho, 2012; Paananen & Lipponen, 2016), provide educators with insights to their curriculum (De Luca et al., 2020; Picchio, 2014) and are used as a catalyst for reflection and a means to review their own pedagogical practice (Lee-Hammond & Bjervås, 2020; Alasuutari, Markström & Vallberg-Roth, 2014). There is limited empirical research on the use of Learning Stories (Blaiklock, 2008) and pedagogical documentation (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021; Cooper, et al., 2014). While these approaches reveal children's learning, they do not assess that learning directly (Emilson & Samuelsson, 2014). Critiques of pedagogical documentation suggest that, as a method of assessment, it is demanding, time consuming (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021) and frequently lacking technical equipment and training for educators (Rintakorpi, 2016).

- Consistent arguments are made through the literature for holistic assessment (developmental and academic) (DeLuca et al., 2020; Cloney, et al., 2019; Alasuutari et al., 2014), which examines both breadth and depth (Hoffman et al., 2014) of children’s learning and development and which includes collaboration and participation of children and families in the assessment process (Scull, 2021). Consequently, a multi-method, multi-informant approach to language assessment in early childhood is the gold standard (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin, 2012).
- The literature questions what is assessed and cautions against an overemphasis on the assessment of constrained or discrete skills (Paris, 2005), which can lead to a narrowing of the curriculum, an approach that compounds existing inequalities (Casbergue, 2011). Johnson et al. (2019) suggest that it is not sufficient to assess skills and knowledge that are already known but it is important to understand children’s mathematical thinking and approaches to mathematical problem solving. Equally in relation to literacy, there is a need for well-informed assessment tools and analysis frames (Clay, 2019), as the sensitivity of some instruments relating to language and vocabulary is lower in relation to younger children (Veldhuizen et al., 2015).
- Seeking to contribute to a ‘civic spirit of accountability’ (Formosinho, 2014 p.111), assessment needs to provide useful and usable information not only for educators and policy makers, but also for children and families.
- The development of the OECD’s International Early Learning Study (IELS) has raised concerns in relation to standardised assessment of preschool children for the purpose of international comparison (Moss & Urban, 2019). The IELS adopts a positivist approach to the exclusion of other theoretical positions in the assessment process (Moss et al., 2016) and fails to recognise or account for the diversity of existing, local educational systems, culture and pedagogical practices. Given the findings from this review, which identify the need for flexible and holistic assessment in early childhood (DeLuca et al., 2020; Cloney, et al., 2019; Marbina et al., 2015; Alasuutari et al., 2014), the IELS continues to draw criticism for its narrow and de-contextualised approach.

Recommendations

Overall, this paper generated recommendations relating to holistic assessment, broader engagement of stakeholders, inclusive assessment practices, literacy and numeracy assessment, and teacher/educator pre-service education as it relates to assessment.

Holistic assessment - The argument is made through the literature for the use of holistic and purposeful assessment approaches and process in early childhood (developmental and academic) (DeLuca et al. 2020; Alasuutari et al. 2014; Visser et al. 2012; Ebbeck 2014) to ensure a comprehensive picture of children's competencies.

Engagement of children and families - Assessment in early childhood should draw on multiple methods and sources of information (LouiseMarbina 2015; Conlon 2002). Children's perspective and voice should be included in assessment (Buzzelli 2018) and their parents also have a critical role in contributing to assessment processes (Verdon et al., 2018; Carr & Lee 2012; Alasuutari et al. 2014; Visser et al. 2012).

Inclusive assessment - Assessment and language assessment specifically must be culturally and socially responsive, specifically for children from diverse backgrounds (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin 2012). There are ongoing shortcomings in assessment instruments as they relate to dual language learners (Soto et al. 2019). A skilled-based approach to assessment often fails to capture the social and cultural practices of linguistically-diverse communities' (Yoon 2015 p. 365) because narrow assessment tools effectively marginalize those children with non-standard language practices (Holmes 2017).

There is a need to develop an appropriate set of assessment instruments for young children with special needs, specifically for those younger than 4 years of age. Instruments available for the developmental assessment of children with motor impairments for example, have insufficient reliability and there is a need to further research the alignment of test results with intervention plans (Visser et al. 2012).

Literacy assessment - While many instruments are available to assess young children's language (Verdon et al., 2018), current assessment approaches do not adequately evidence the complexities of literacy development. Language assessment of young children should view the child holistically and include a thorough consideration of other areas of functioning (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin 2012). Visser et al. (2012) posit the value of combining standardised test results with information from qualitative instruments, for example observations and parent reports. Teale et al., (2020) caution that early literacy assessment requires further study and warns against the overuse of assessments in preschool.

Numeracy assessment - There is a dearth of literature, specifically systematic reviews or literature reviews, in relation to the assessment of mathematics in early childhood. Further research is required into broadening notions of what counts as mathematics and how mathematics can be taught to young children (Johnson et al. 2019). In addition, a broader range of assessment tools that specifically address numeracy in early childhood must be developed (Johnson et al. 2019; Franke, et al., 2020) cognisant of understanding not only discrete mathematical skills but also mathematical thinking and language. The interaction between age, culture, home numeracy and mathematical skills is worthy of further investigation given the home influence on the developing child (Mutaf-Yildiz et al. 2020).

Teachers/Educators - Many of the recommendations emanating from this paper relate to both instruments and the skills of the teacher/educator in undertaking assessments. Educators in ECEC need to understand the different ways in which children learn (Tickell 2011; Hussain, Woods & Williams 2019) and they should also have the relevant expertise in language development and language assessment to allow them to make appropriate selections, observations, administrations and interpretations of information provided by the tools and the methods they use (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin 2012). Educators must be able to observe and record behaviours across multiple domains of development (Losardo & Notari Syverson 2011) such as cognitive, affective and psycho-motor (Drifte 2002). The demands on teachers/educators in relation to assessment speak to the need for assessment and documentation to have a strong emphasis during preservice preparation and subsequent and ongoing in-service Professional Development/Learning (Buldu, 2010).

Narrative Report

This report focuses on assessment in Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC). After a systematic search in academic databases, 12 relevant systematic reviews were identified. The corpus consists of 26 relevant articles, reports and handbooks to cover areas where no systematic reviews were identified. This section reports on the findings around the different purposes, strategies, approaches, practices and tools for assessment of learning and dispositions. While the focus is on literacy and numeracy, the narrative takes a wider approach to assessment in ECE, given the holistic nature of education of young children.

Research Questions

- What strategies or approaches support the assessment of young children's literacies, numeracy and learning dispositions?
- What practices and tools support assessment in ECEC?
- Who is involved in the assessment process of young children?
- What is the child's role in the assessment process?
- What are the new developments in early childhood education assessment and evaluation practices?

Assessment in early childhood education and care (ECEC)

The term, concept and discourse of assessment in early childhood is ambiguous (Alasuutari et al., 2014). It may mean to evaluate or analyse something, to estimate, to give a review, assess or rate someone or something (Vallberg-Roth 2012, p. 1). In terms of education, assessment is generally understood as 'all those activities undertaken by teachers [educators] and by their students [children] in assessing themselves, which provide information to be used as feedback to modify the teaching and learning activities in which they are engaged (Black & William 1998, p.2). Assessment in early childhood is concerned with the processes of collecting information about children drawing on various forms of evidence and then organising and interpreting that information to make judgements about children's development and learning (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021).

There are multiple and varying practical and theoretical perspectives on assessment and the ways in which it is used to evaluate, diagnose, plan and communicate children's learning (Wortham & Hardin, 2016). Policy makers may see assessment as a means of accountability, of determining quality and of informing policy development (Basford & Bath, 2014), while parents and educators will understand assessment as a way of determining what children know or can do and what they need to support learning and development (Casbergue 2011).

Assessment in early childhood may be focused on individual children (Hussain et al., 2019) or group activities or at a setting level (ECEC or school), that is, in relation to early childhood settings and/or educators. In Nordic countries, for example, assessment is a culturally contradictory issue (Alasuutari et al. 2012, p.3,) with assessment understood as part of the formal school system for children at ages 6 or 7 years, while in England 4-year-old children on entry to primary school, undertake a formal Baseline Assessment (Roberts-Holmes & Bradbury 2017). Assessment may also be used to focus on the curriculum and pedagogical practices of ECEC settings, examining the ways in which children's learning and development are supported (Vallberg-Roth 2011). Picchio et al. (2014) propose that assessment in early childhood is not intended to take account of what children know or can do but rather approaches such as pedagogical documentation should be used to evaluate the quality of ECEC practice and provision (i.e., for Centre or System evaluation).

Assessment can be indirect, drawing on a range of informal, narrative type approaches (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021) whereby educators observe children in their natural environment as they play and interact. Assessment can also be direct or standardised and, if appropriate, 'can offer rich information about individuals, as well as groups of children' (van Hemel & Snow 2008, p. 17).

Assessment is presented as complex, having many purposes, involving differing stakeholders and drawing on a range of formal and informal instruments. Drawing on the literature, this paper will examine the conceptualisations, paradigms, perspectives and politics of assessment in early childhood, along with consideration of who should be involved in assessment processes and exploration of formal and informal approaches in assessing literacy, numeracy and digital literacies.

Conceptualisations of assessment in ECEC

Assessment in early childhood can be conceptualised as being summative (assessment of learning), formative (assessment of learning) (Cameron et al., 2018), or transformative (Vallberg-Roth, 2012). Much of the literature in early childhood focuses on holistic assessment and draws on a combination of approaches.

Formative assessment can be understood as, ‘assessment for learning’, that is as a valuation of what happens during the learning process (Carr 2009; McLachlan et al., 2013). It is forward-looking, aims to support the ongoing learning and development of children and is underpinned by the active involvement of the child, the family and the educators (Alasuutari et al., 2014). Observations, Learning Stories, Portfolios and Pedagogical Documentation are all associated with formative assessment. Formative assessment is not without critique, with Bennet (2011) questioning the looseness and effectiveness of the approach.

Summative assessment, often considered as ‘assessment of learning’, refers to a valuation of what children have learnt at the end of an activity or period. It takes a retrospective look at learning, which may be based on a number of forms of assessment and it may incorporate an element of scoring or grading. Summative assessment requires the educator to make judgements about what children were able to do or knew at a particular point in time (Bennett 2011). Summative assessment may draw on standardised and diagnostic tests that are designed to identify strengths and difficulties (Boyle & Fisher, 2007) by providing information about how a child is developing in relation to a larger group of children of the same chronological age (Losardo & Notari Syverson 2011; Hussain et al., 2019). Miles et al. (2018) proposed that difficulties arise when using standardised assessment with younger children because such tests do not match the developmental characteristics of preschool children, which results in and is related to reliability issues.

Assessment is also conceptualised in early childhood not merely ‘for’ learning, or ‘of’ learning but ‘as learning’ (DeLuca et al., 2020), where educators recognise the process of assessment as a powerful tool to support children’s development and learning. From this perspective, assessment draws on discussions with children and documenting learning with educators, enabling children to recognise themselves as learners, identify their strengths and develop understanding of how they learn (Ebbeck et al., 2014; Clark 2012).

Transformative assessment (Vallberg-Roth 2011; Vallberg-Roth & Månsson 2008) is a concept that may describe and capture the complex assessment and documentation practices that appear in the literature. Transformative assessment recognises the value and necessity of a multi-documentation approach and is an interplay between linear (goal-directed) and nonlinear (rhizomatic) assessment (Alasuutari, et. al., 2014, p. 50). The concept of transformative assessment accommodates the differing formats, functions and participants involved in the assessment process. The actors not only include children, educators and parents but also can refer to broader community engagement.

Assessment is closely linked with understandings of learning and development. Learning in early childhood is conceptualised as complex and nonlinear (Marbina et al 2015; Sharmahad & Peeters 2019), with learning experiences understood as a set of affordances or opportunities and not as a series of pre-programmed steps (Pascal & Bertram, 2016). It follows that dynamic assessment processes are required to match this early childhood education reality. The literature highlights that assessment cannot be decoupled from the philosophy and curriculum of the setting (Alasuutari et al., 2014) and it cannot be considered in isolation from the conditions under which the performance is assessed (Van Hemel & Snow, 2008). Moreover, a constant theme through the literature foregrounds the need for a holistic approach that draws on a range of tools, depending on the purpose of the assessment.

Assessment paradigms and perspectives

In the literature, the different purposes and processes of assessment can be linked to two established and contrasting paradigms, which are referred to in various forms: positivist, developmental, standardised or prescribed, and sociocultural, learning-based and open. More contemporary approaches position assessment as democratic (involving), participatory and moral practices. Despite the separation of approaches to assessment, Cloney et al. (2019) argue, as do others (Alasuutari, et. al. 2014; Vallberg-Roth 2011) for educators in early childhood to be open to different philosophies and to have access to a broad range of tools to ensure children's learning and development is supported.

Developmental approaches to assessment in ECEC

Standardised or prescribed forms of assessment 'are designed to identify strengths and difficulties by providing information about how a child is developing in relation to a larger group of children of the same chronological age' (Hussain 2019, p. 2). Developmental assessment tools, associated with standardised testing, have traditionally been used to

monitor children's development, identify special needs and report to external stakeholders (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin 2012). In the area of special needs standardised assessments are deemed essential (Visser et al., 2012) as early detection of developmental problems enable the timely provision of supports for children and parents. In terms of literacy that means assessing expressive and receptive language skills (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin 2012); general vocabulary and specific word measures (Hoffman et al., 2014); phonological and short-term memory abilities and multiple dimensions of language (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin 2012; Soto et al. 2019). Standardised assessment in relation to numeracy is associated with assessing discrete elements of mathematics, for example, symbolic number skills and non-symbolic arithmetic (Raghubar & Barnes 2017) and number sense (Butterworth et al., 2011). The skills and competencies most frequently assessed within a standardised approach are 'constrained skills', that is discrete sets of knowledge or competencies (Paris, 2005), for example being able to recite the alphabet or the ability to isolate initial phonemes in spoken words (Casbergue 2011, p.13) or being able to identify numbers (Gobel et al. 2014).

These tools have gained popularity in the last decades, although they have received numerous criticisms in the ECE field. In their review of the literature, Visser et al. (2012) highlight that in general, work needs to be done to improve the quality of the instruments available for children younger than 4 years of age (Visser et al. 2012, 120). They note that for young children reliability, suitability of assessment instruments, and test duration are factors that must be considered in the assessment process. Equally, in considering developmental assessment tools, Conlon (2002) proposes that children's competencies should be included in the assessment, while Visser et al. (2012) posit the value of combining standardised test results with information from qualitative instruments, for example observations and parent reports.

Sociocultural approaches to assessment in ECEC

Open-type approaches to assessment in early childhood emerge from a sociocultural perspective, and understand it as an integral component of teaching and learning; 'a dynamic, ongoing process, which only becomes effective when there is collaboration between parents and early childhood professionals' (Ntuli et al., 2014). Open-type approaches may be used to document children's learning, guide curriculum planning and decision making, and communicate with families and other stakeholders (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021). In contrast to the assessment of constrained skills within a developmental frame, an open, sociocultural approach focuses on examining children's unconstrained skills (Casbergue, 2011), which

acknowledge that external factors such as the environment (Harms & Clifford, 2005), social emotional and physical growth all impact on learning. From an ecological perspective, Johnson et al. (2019) suggest that it is not sufficient to assess skills and knowledge that are already known but it is important to understand children's mathematical thinking and approaches to mathematical problem solving. Thus, more open approaches tend to account for the context of children's learning within the assessment process. Laevers and Verboven (2000), for example, advocate for a process-orientated approach to assessment, focusing on children's levels of well-being and involvement. Laevers (2000) asserts that involvement and well-being are prerequisites to deep level learning and his project *Experiential Learning* (Laevers, 1999) offers strategies and scales to assist in assessing children's wellbeing and involvement. Equally, rather than assessing discrete skills, Carr and Claxton (2002) focus on examining dispositions as enablers in the learning process. Dispositions can be thought of as habits of mind, or tendencies to respond to situations in certain ways' (Katz, 1988, p. 30) and Carr (2001) has proposed that in relation to assessment in early childhood, learning dispositions can be conceptualised as children being ready, willing and able to engage in learning. Young children's dispositions become evident in the ways they respond over time to learning opportunities and challenges. Literature affirms the importance of dispositional learning (Carr & Lee 2012; Daniels, 2013) with Cooper et al. (2014) suggesting that teachers need to develop an understanding of how children develop learning dispositions. However, while it is important to recognise and develop children's learning dispositions, there is a difficulty in identifying which dispositions should be nurtured and assessed (Dunphy 2010). Claxton (1999) identifies dispositions which relate to the development of young children's literacy and numeracy and these he names as 'learnacy', that is curiosity, mindfulness, selectivity, resilience, experimentation, reflection, opportunism and conviviality. Despite acknowledgement of the importance of disposition in children's learning, Carr (2001) acknowledges the challenges involved in tracking and assessing them.

Contemporary approaches to assessment in ECEC

Contemporary perspectives point towards assessment in early childhood being considered as democratic practice (Moss, 2011), participatory pedagogy (Formosino & Pascal 2016), and as a moral practice (Buzzelli, 2018). Democratic practices in ECEC allow for children and adults to have a voice in shaping decisions that impact on them. It means sharing control and power so that the adult is not always the one with the right answer

(Rinaldi, 2006). Assessment as a participatory pedagogy, adheres to the philosophical principle of assessment providing for the greater good of all, ensuring that useful and meaningful information is derived for children, families, professionals, educational settings and policy makers and that assessment contributes to a civic spirit of accountability (Fomoshino & Pascal, 2016). Assessment as a moral practice must be done from two perspectives: from the learner's perspective, to assess children's agency in guiding their own learning, and in looking to the environment, to assess the opportunities for learning afforded children by the environment. Balancing assessment is a moral challenge for teachers (Buzzelli, 2018).

In considering assessment from multiple perspectives the literature suggests that no one approach can satisfy all requirements. An overemphasis on the assessment of constrained or discrete skills can lead to a narrowing of the curriculum and teaching to the test, an approach that compounds existing social inequalities (Casbergue 2011) and does not allow for children's strengths or funds of knowledge (Hedges et al., 2011) to emerge in the assessment process. From a sociocultural perspective, it is acknowledged that rigid assessments do not adequately account for children's home contexts; for example, studies consistently show that socio-economic status is positively related to literacy, from emergent literacy up to the commencement of formal schooling (Molfese et al., 2003), through primary/elementary school (Feinstein and Bynner, 2004; Kieffer 2010) and into high school (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2010).

In contrast, many teachers seek to assess learning more broadly by examining children's understanding of print forms and functions (Carbergue, 2011), and numeracy behaviours in a range of contexts (Johnson et al., 2019). The more open approaches to assessment have been critiqued (Bennett 2011) as being loose, a work in progress and circumspect in terms of efficacy. In short Bennett (2011) suggests that further work and research is required to realise the potential of these forms of assessment.

The argument is consistently made through the literature for holistic assessment (developmental and academic) (DeLuca et al., 2020; Alasuutari et al., 2014) that examines both breadth and depth (Hoffman et al., 2014) of children's learning and development.

Politics of assessment in ECEC

Assessment in early childhood is never neutral and is closely linked with understandings of learning and development (Pascal & Bertram, 2016). Stakeholders will hold differing perspectives on the purpose of assessment and the ways in which it is used to evaluate, diagnose, plan curriculum and communicate with families (Wortham & Hardin, 2016). Policy makers may see assessment as a means of accountability (Basford & Bath, 2014) while parents and educators will understand it as a way of determining what children know or can do and what they need to support learning and development (Casbergue, 2011).

Across assessment paradigms, processes and perspectives, part of the literature suggests that educators get caught up in ‘playing a game’ whereby they try to integrate the requirements of various stakeholders in their daily practice (Basford & Bath, 2014). As identified earlier in this paper, standardised assessments have been strongly criticised (Auld & Morris, 2019; Basford & Bath, 2014; Brunsek et al., 2017; Fundus, 2015; Hussain et al., 2019; Perlman, 2016; Robert-Holmes, 2017, 2019; Yoon, 2015). First, they are said to impose restrictions on practice, limiting the understanding of children and failing to engage with the wider social context of the child (Hussain et al., 2019). Second, standardised assessments are criticised for drawing on discourse of readiness and achievement gaps, which mask issues of social and economic exclusion (Robert-Holmes, 2017; Yoon, 2015): Readiness demands that children grasp a defined skills set, deemed rigorous, with timely developmental progressions. Following this logic, assessment practices created a separation and grouping of children according to ability levels (Yoon, 2015). Bradbury (2011) extends the argument even further and adds that standardised assessments not only reflect inequality, but also help (re)create it. An illustrative example is the baseline assessment in England. The assessment measures children’s developmental process from reception until the end of key stage 2 (KS2). The Baseline Assessment facilitates comparison through its potential to hierarchically rank children, schools and local authorities. As Robert-Holmes argues:

The potentially damaging effect of baseline assessment is that for children with low scores (‘below typical’), even if they make good progress, it will be seen as acceptable for them to remain low attaining at age 11. This is a problem inherent in any ‘value-added’ measure where the baseline is known and is more likely to affect those groups who are lower attaining within the system in general, such as ethnic minorities, children receiving free school meals, children with SEN and EAL, and some summer-born children. (Robert-Holmes & Bradbury 2017, p. 3-4)

This happens in a context where initiatives to introduce standardised comparisons to measure performance in ECEC are on the rise. Baseline Assessment, as well as the International Early Learning Study (IELS) promoted by the OECD, are part of a ‘datafication’ and ‘dataveillance’ of education, which is now reaching ECE (Roberts-Holmes 2019). The IELS, developed by the OECD, is a standardised assessment of preschool children for the purpose of international comparison (Moss & Urban, 2019). The OECD indicates that the IELS comprises of a mix of direct and indirect assessment of children at age 5 years, with the direct assessment element measuring four specific learning domains. However, the IELS has drawn critique internationally (Moss & Urban, 2019; Carr et al., 2016; Moss et al., 2016) for its democratic deficit, ethical and methodological flaws (Urban, 2019).

Criticisms predominantly centre on the positivistic approach, adopted by the IELS, which is developmental in nature and excludes other disciplinary and theoretical positions (Moss et al., 2016). The IELS is further critiqued for its reductionist approach, which disregards culturally embedded educational practices and complex early childhood education and care systems that currently exist (Moss et al., 2016; Urban, 2019). A third critique of the IELS focuses on the neglect of context in undertaking comparative analyses of young children in diverse early childhood systems. As Alexander (2012, p.5) suggests “national education systems, are embedded in national culture”, which explains why “no educational policy or practice can be properly understood except by reference to the web of inherited ideas and values, habits and customs, institutions and world views, that make one country distinct from another”. Given the findings from this review, which identify the need for flexible and holistic assessment in early childhood (DeLuca et al., 2020; Cloney, et al., 2019; Marbina et al., 2015; Alasuutari et al., 2014) the IELS raises concerns.

These criticisms are strong in relation to literacy, where standardised assessment tools or approaches are often seen as having a number of limitations. First, part of the literature suggests standardised assessment tools and strategies decontextualise literacy acquisition. In fact, literacy is socioculturally constructed and it is used in specific contexts. Yoon (2015) claims that standardised tests ‘often reflect a skills-based approach to language that fails to capture the social and cultural practices of linguistically diverse communities’ (p. 365) and Bradbury and Roberts-Holmes (2017) argue that narrow assessment tools marginalise those with non-typical or non-standard language practices. Second, standardised literacy tests,

especially those that are group administered, are also criticised in the literature as ‘being so unlike normal literacy activity that they make no sense to children’ (Casbergue 2015, p. 17).

Following the literature, we could argue that standardised assessments should be critically interrogated when introduced in ECEC. It is important to understand the principles that underpin the development and implementation of these tools. With that clarity, they may be used for certain purposes mentioned earlier.

Some prescribed assessment tools and strategies, which are reviewed in the following section, may be useful for educators in some situations. As Marbina et al. (2015) point out: ‘by drawing on multiple methods and sources of information – including the individual child, whole group and centre level, and the inclusion of children and parents’ reports and knowledge – a more authentic understanding (...) can be gained (p. 19). We argue that both open-ended and prescribed tools can be part of the ‘toolkit’ that ECEC educators need to have to best serve the rights and needs of young children.

Assessment for and with whom

There is a broad consensus in contemporary ECEC literature emphasising the importance of including the voice of children and families in the assessment process (Scull et al, 2021). The participation of children and families in assessment is particularly important as it relates to the domains of literacy and numeracy, two pillars in the development of young children. In order to achieve full participation, assessment practices need to actively involve children and consider the voice of families using democratic and participatory strategies (Formosinho, 2014). Seeking to contribute to a ‘civic spirit of accountability’ (Formosinho, 2014 p.111), assessment needs to provide useful and usable information not only for educators and policy makers, but also for children and families.

However, the systematic reviews and other sources consulted argue that, in ECEC, children’s voices are not always included in the assessment of their own learning (Zhang, 2017). Ebbeck (2014) highlights however that children should be active participants in the planning and gathering of assessment information to document their own learning process. Buzzelli (2018) identifies the benefits of positioning students at the centre of the assessment process, as it supports the integration of informed teaching practices and the development of relevant knowledge and skills in children. It is interesting to note that children’s voices can help improve assessment, as they identify areas of knowledge that are not captured by many

assessment approaches; Johnson et al. (2019) highlights that an important part of young children's mathematical thinking typically goes unmeasured.

Furthermore, existing research has rarely explored the involvement of families in ECEC assessment. Assessment documents children's learning through multiple methods and sources for a broad audience. Thus, the communication between school and home is a vital part of assessment (Buzzelli, 2018). Research evidence establishes the importance of families in children's learning, but often families are positioned as 'consumers of, rather than active knowledgeable participants, in assessment' (Cooper et al., 2014, p.794).

Participatory assessment processes involve all relevant stakeholders

'within an educational context systematically gathering evidence to gain greater knowledge, understanding and confidence to make constructive changes for the better. It is an internally led, subjective and deeply attached process rather than an externally driven, objective, detached process' (Bertram & Pascal 2014, p. 62 in Formosinho 2014).

With a participatory approach, a variety of tools and strategies can be used. Open type tools and strategies, which are described in detail in the following section, can involve all stakeholders in the assessment process.

Approaches to Assessment of Literacy, Numeracy and Digital Literacy in ECEC

Literacy

There is a recognition that literacy learning takes place in the years prior to formal schooling and that young children develop literacy-like behaviours through exposure to interactions in shared contexts in which literacy is a component (Scull et al., 2021). Shifting perspectives of literacy development in early childhood link closely with evolving views of emergent literacy assessment (Casbergue, 2011). How literacy is understood has a direct impact on the forms of assessment and subsequent interventions. A readiness perspective, grounded in Piagetian developmentalism, assesses whether children can discriminate among sounds heard in oral language and when they know which letters represent those sounds. A constructivist approach assesses for evidence of how children understand print, its forms, functions and meanings. This approach is concerned with how children use language. The path to reading is complex and begins with strong early literacy skills that include phonological awareness or the manipulation and synthesis of spoken words at the word,

syllable, and phonemic levels (Soto et al., 2019). Conversely, there is a need for well-informed assessment tools and analysis frames (Clay, 2019), that requires integration of information from a variety of sources (parents, educators and children) to match the complex learning processes of becoming literate.

Literature highlights communication, language and vocabulary as significant elements in the development of children's literacy. A range of assessment tools and approaches that support these elements of literacy development are explored below.

Communication

The most rapid period of speech and language development occurs during the first five years of life (McLeod & Baker, 2017), with the development of communication and other specific skills happening in nonlinear trajectories and differing timeframes. Equally, children with different cultural and linguistic backgrounds may have varying styles of communication and educators must be cognisant in drawing on established assessment techniques (Verdon et al., 2018). In their paper, Verdon et al. (2018) identify seven assessment typologies in considering children as communicators: screening; criterion-referenced; dynamic; standardised; norm-referenced; progress monitoring; and outcome measurement, many of which overlap in practice. They also present a comprehensive list of 10 validated assessment tools, which can be used by early childhood professionals to assess children's communication capabilities. The communication assessment tools as reported by Verdon et al. (2018), cover the age range 0-8 years and include: Ages and Stages Questionnaire (ASQ-3) (Squires et al., 2009); Focus on the Outcomes of Communication Under Six (FOCUS) (Thomas-Stonell et al., 2012); Infant-Toddler Social and Emotional Assessment (ITSEA) (Briggs-Gowan Carter, 1998); Intelligibility in Context Scale (ICS) (McLeod, Harrison & McCormack, 2012a) and McArthur-Bates Communicative Development Inventories (CDI) (Fenson et al., 2007). These instruments are parent (or educator) reported and provide initial screening. All are valid but there may be evidence that the sensitivity of the ASQ-3 is lower in relation to younger children (Veldhuizen et al., 2015).

Language

Assessment of language abilities in preschool children should involve an evaluation of both expressive and receptive skills and should include an evaluation of more than one

dimension of language (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin, 2012). Law et al. (2010) make strong arguments for the early detection of language impairments in young children. However, this is challenging as there are few definitive predictors of language difficulties and available instruments are neither sensitive nor specific enough (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin, 2012) to assess language in early childhood.

Language cannot be assumed to be a discrete and readily measurable property. Challenges arise in assessing children's language, as it is a joint and social process that involves interacting with others. Children's language will vary depending on the audience or partner, the gender of the child and the gender of the conversational partner or parent (Lovas, 2011). Preschool children are known to behave linguistically differently in different contexts and with different interactive partners, depending on the environment and context, for example the child may not be monolingual and there may be cultural variations in how children interpret and respond to interaction with another (strange) adult.

Expressive and receptive language skills involve different cortical areas and difficulties in one area do not automatically imply problems with the other. It is therefore important to assess both language production and understanding, as the assessment of a single element alone can be misleading. There are a range of assessment instruments which examine discrete aspects of language and allow for a narrow focus. Two established instruments for assessing the language of young children (under 3 years of age) are the Preschool Language Scale (Zimmerman et al., 1979) and the Rice/Wexler Test of Early Grammar Impairment (Rice & Wexler, 2001). The British Picture Vocabulary Scale Third Edition (Dunn and Dunn, 2009) and the Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test Fourth Edition (Dunn and Dunn, 2007) measure receptive language. Tools that use parental reports and observation are also effective for very young children, for example, MacArthur-Bates Communicative Development Inventories Second Edition (CDI) (Fenson et al., 2007).

The use of formal tools such as standardised tests complemented with more informal assessment strategies, such as naturalistic observations, is likely to provide a more meaningful evaluation of the child's language skills (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin, 2012). Elements of language to be assessed include: expressive and receptive language skills; phonology; lexicon; semantics; grammar; pragmatics and discourse. Language assessment should be culturally appropriate, taking into consideration linguistic, social and economic factors. Language assessment of preschool children should view the child as a whole and

include a thorough consideration of other areas of functioning. Consequently, a multi-method, multi-informant approach to language assessment in early childhood is the gold standard (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin, 2012).

Vocabulary

There is consensus in early childhood education that vocabulary is important and that reading aloud supports literacy (Hoffman et al., 2014) but that there are problems in how vocabulary is assessed.

The Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (PPVT; Dunn and Dunn, 2007), the Expressive One Word Picture Voc-2 (EOWPVT; Brownell, 2000), and the Expressive Vocabulary Test (EVT-2, Williams, 2007) are tools that are valid and reliable, normed and standardised; and easy to learn and use by educators. Gains in vocabulary learning or acquisition, attributed to instruction, are small but important and Hoffman et al. (2014) raise concerns about the ‘relative insensitivity of general vocabulary measures’ (p.466). Challenges arise, for example, where picture-based assessments are used as they comprise mainly of nouns with few verbs and adjectives or where children have multiple choice and even taking into account the probability of achieving correct answers by chance, the practical significance of the scores can be uncertain. Other forms of assessment, for example the administration of yes/no questions (Beck & McKeown, 2007), can confuse young children and prompt them to respond with what they feel the teacher/educator wants or expects.

Definitional measures are an underutilised approach to assessing young children’s vocabulary. It involves prompting children to use their own language in explaining word meanings. While this approach offers insights into children’s language, it is challenging for educators/teachers to score (Hoffman et al., 2014). Neither yes/no nor definitional measures manage to overcome the complexities in assessing vocabulary in early childhood. Teale et al., (2020) conclude that early literacy assessment requires further study and caution against the overuse of preschool assessments in the United States.

Traditional or standardised assessment which seek to evaluate programme effectiveness, identify children's attainment levels or make comparisons of children's performances have been critiqued as not making sense to children and consequently are not reliable (Casbergue, 2011, p.17). There is also concern in relation to what is assessed. Traditional assessments or standardized tests tend to examine isolated skills in

decontextualized contexts. Many of the limitations associated with standardised or traditional assessment can be avoided through the use of documentation and/or observational assessment, which allow for assessment in naturalistic or embedded contexts.

Numeracy

Longitudinal studies have shown that children's mathematical knowledge at school entry is the strongest predictor of both later math success as well as success in other academic domains (Raghubar & Barnes, 2017). Raghubar and Barnes (2017) suggest that direct assessment of early numeracy skills is important given the association with later mathematical achievement. Assessment of early math skills should include measures of numerical symbol knowledge such as number identification based on numerals and arrays, counting emphasising cardinality and ordinality (Merkley & Ansari, 2016) and manipulation of non-symbolic number (Raghubar & Barnes, 2017). However, assessment tools of this nature are not available as separate normative-based tests and brief, easy to score screening instruments for assessing preschool math and early years' math-specific vocabulary are yet to be developed (Purpura et al., 2015).

Given the paucity of appropriate maths assessment instruments for preschool, it is worthwhile highlighting the results of a systematic review (652 articles) undertaken by Mutaf-Yildiz et al. (2020) which showed a positive association between home numeracy and children's mathematical skills. This may have relevance for young children in early childhood settings, where educators and parents work closely in partnership. Assessment methods used in the home consisted of comprehensive questionnaires (Le Fevre et al., 2009) and observations (Levine et al., 2010). The challenge for this form of mathematical-focused assessment is that questionnaires are retrospective and rely on memory (subject to bias) and observations are self-reported. Both methods of assessment require further research and may have some relevance for ECEC.

Arising from their study, which attempted to highlight preschoolers' understanding of counting, Johnson et al. (2019, p.238) propose that 'young children are remarkably capable of engaging in and making sense of sophisticated mathematical ideas'. They deduced that much of what children know about counting is not noted or captured and consequently their mathematical capabilities are underestimated. Johnson et al. (2019) eschew the notion of narrowing mathematical curricula or assessment processes. It is important to broaden the concept of mathematics, attend to the details of children's counting and begin to understand

their thinking. Current assessment practices are not adequately reflecting what children can do mathematically. Future developments in teaching, curriculum and assessment processes must be more responsive and build on what children already know (Franke et al., 2020).

Digital Literacies

Little data and few studies emerged through the literature review in relation to assessment of digital literacies in preschool children. In a 2020 study, Teale et al. proposed that, despite significant developments and enhanced understandings of digital technologies, little research currently exists on its use or assessment in the classroom. Teale et al. (2020) suggest that this situation will change in the coming years as there is a time lag involved in the adoption of new practices and technologies in the classroom and consequently, it will take time for studies to appear in the literature. There is also a suggestion that different questions need to be asked and different approaches to interpreting the learning and benefits of digital technologies are required if ‘we are to be able to communicate the dynamic nature of what is happening in early childhood’ (Teale et al., 2020, p.204).

Crescenzi-Lanna (2020, p.1485) highlights that ‘Analytics and Multimodal Learning Analytics (MMLA), is the measurement, collection, analysis and reporting of data about learners and their context for the purposes of understanding and optimizing learning and the environments in which it occurs’. She advises that MMLA supports the learning process but that very few studies have focused on young children, potentiality due to the complexity of conducting non-obtrusive research and the fact that children may not be capable of completing questionnaires or following detailed instructions. A systematic review of the literature on this topic suggests that to date the role of technology in learning analytics has been firmly focused on older children with the purposes of ‘assessment feedback’, prediction and intervention’ or ‘monitoring and analysis’ (Agus & Samuri, 2018, p.41). MMLA offers opportunities for understanding children's learning differently, providing ‘a window into what really happens during the student learning path’ (Agus & Samuri, 2018, p.36). However, the effectiveness of face and speech recognition technology that can track and analyse the learning processes of young children is in its infancy.

Challenges are anticipated in the use of technology in the assessment of young children. The level of data generated far exceeds the time teachers have available to interpret and use the information productively as part of pedagogical practice. The cost of technology resources can be prohibitive, for example, eye tracking glasses or bracelets, as can the time

and training that educators/teachers require. Ethical issues arise in relation to the sharing of digital data and the ability of teachers and researchers to provide anonymity. Some of the technology, e.g., eye glasses, would be intrusive for children and would be in opposition to the concept of authentic assessment. However, biometric wristbands for example are more affordable, less intrusive and could provide biometric data which could be supported, or triangulated with observations and other forms of assessment. While the use of digital technology within an assessment process is possible (Crescenzi-Lanna, 2020), the question might be if it is desirable.

Informal Assessment Strategies in ECEC

Pyle and DeLuca (2013) highlight the dearth of empirical research into assessment practices in early childhood classrooms. They recognise that while traditional assessment in early childhood has taken the form of a diagnostic-formative-summative approach, this is problematic with the emergence of more contemporary conceptualisations of assessment as, for and of learning.

The validated instruments and developmental approaches which assess literacy and to a much lesser extent numeracy, attempt to assess children's specific skills and knowledge. In contrast, and evident through a systematic review of literature (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021), dissatisfaction with traditional approaches to assessment has led to a broadening of participation in the assessment process, greater visibility of children's learning and an increase in what might be considered informal and alternative assessment approaches (Alaçam & Olgan, 2016). These informal assessment approaches focus on children's holistic learning and development, emphasising strengths and learning dispositions. Child observation and documentation are established approaches to assessment in early childhood (Alasuutarai et al., 2014), with informal assessment relying on information gleaned from observing children in naturalistic play situations.

Play and learning are commonly described partners in the early years (Grindheim & Ødegaard, 2013). In play children learn and develop at their own pace (Weisberg et al., 2013). It provides a context for personal, social and academic learning (Van Oers & Duijkers, 2013) and has been found to support the development of self-regulation (Berk & Meyers, 2013) and early literacy skills (Roskos & Christie, 2013). However, while a substantial body of literature highlights the importance of learning and play in early childhood (Dunphy, 2010;

Van Oers & Duijkers, 2013), research on embedded assessment practices in the classroom is rare (Gullo & Hughes, 2011; Roach, 2010). In the classroom, educators are required to monitor and support children's learning through integrating assessment and using findings to enrich pedagogy (Gullo & Hughes, 2011) and this has led to an increase in diagnostic and formative assessment practices (Buldu, 2010; Clark, 2012; Gullo & Hughes, 2011; William, 2011) in early childhood. A body of literature cautions against the narrowing of assessment to specific skills (Pyle & DeLuca, 2017) and play-based assessment offers opportunities for continual assessment that draws on multiple tools or formats and which reflects children's learning in the context of curriculum goals (Gullo & Hughes, 2011). Comprehensive and holistic assessment can best be gained through observation and participation (Wolfendale, 2000; Losardo and Notari Syverson, 2011) to determine children's strengths and weaknesses. Play-based assessment is also accessible to parents, children and other professionals.

Observation and Learning Stories

Observing is a core pedagogical practice and assessment technique in early childhood. Observation or assessment aligns with the Aistear, the Early Childhood Curriculum Framework (2009) and takes many forms, using open or template narratives and multimedia tools such as videos (taken with digital cameras) and photographs (Carr & Lee, 2012).

Learning Stories is one method of observation and assessment which was developed by Carr (2001), expanded on with her colleagues (Carr & Lee, 2012; Carr et al., 2010) and which has grown a global following. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) reported that 11 out of 20 countries use 'storytelling' in ECE (defined as 'examples of work and feedback that tell the story of the child's development during a certain period of time') (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2015, p.176).

Learning Stories are considered as an assessment tool where adults and children tell and retell stories of learning and competence, reflecting on the past and planning for the future (Carr & Lee, 2012). They assess children's learning dispositions (Cooper, Hedges & Dixon, 2014), which Carr (2001) suggests are about being ready, willing and able to engage in learning. Learning Stories promote children's capacity for self-reflection and self-education (Liljestrand & Hammarberg, 2017; De Luca et al., 2020). A central tenet of Learning Stories is that teachers involve children as active agents in the selection of learning

activities and in the assessment of their participation in those activities (Buzzelli, 2019). Learning Stories makes it possible for children's agency to be seen, heard, and experienced by themselves and others. The documentation process also involves parents, educators, other adults and peers, who have a significant role in children's learning (Cooper, Hedges & Dixon, 2014).

A strength of the Learning Stories approach lies in its alignments with a bi-cultural curriculum (New Zealand [NZ] Ministry of Education, 2017) and the ability of those using this approach to effectively gather data from immigrant children (Ntuli et al., 2014). Through involving children, parents and educators in the assessment process, Learning Stories avoid problematic issues that have arisen in other contexts, 'language barriers, cultural clashes, socio-economic factors and culturally and linguistically biased assessment measures' (Ntuli, Nyarambi & Traore's, 2014, p.221).

The Learning Stories approach is not without its detractors. For some, the ways in which parents are involved in the process of assessing children's learning is called into question (Cooper et al., 2014). Equally, there are long-standing criticisms, with Blaiklock (2008) arguing that Learning Stories is a problematic form of assessment, particularly for literacy. He contends that it has not yet been established if learning stories are an effective, valid, reliable and practical means of assessing and enhancing children's learning.

Documentation

Pedagogical documentation is well established in early childhood. It can be considered as both content (written notes, observations, audio/video recordings, photographs, artwork and displays) and process, that is using the materials as a basis for reflection with and amongst educators, children and parents (Lee-Hammond & Bjervås, 2020). Pedagogical documentation serves many purposes, but is primarily a formative assessment technique which seeks to understand the experiences of children, which makes children's learning visible to others and which allows children themselves to make meaning of their learning experiences (Oliveira-Formosinho & Formosinho, 2012; Paananen & Lipponen, 2016). Pedagogical documentation also provides educators with insights to their curriculum (De Luca et al., 2019; Picchio et al., 2014) and is used as a catalyst for reflection and a means to review their own pedagogical practice (Lee-Hammond & Bjervås, 2020; Alasuutari et al., 2014).

There is limited empirical research on the use of pedagogical documentation in early childhood education (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021) and while it reveals children's learning, it does not assess that learning directly (Emilson & Samuelsson, 2014). Critiques of pedagogical documentation suggest that as a method of assessment it is demanding, time consuming (Alaçam & Olgan, 2021) and frequently lacking technical equipment and training for educators (Rintakorpi, 2016).

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Author Bios

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Appendix

Key Search Terms

(assessment OR evaluation OR assessing) AND ("early years" OR "early childhood education" OR "kindergarten" OR "preschool" OR "nursery") AND ("systematic review" OR review OR "best evidence" OR "meta-analysis" OR "literature review") AND (literacy OR numeracy)

(assessment OR evaluation OR assessing) AND ("early years" OR "early childhood education" OR "kindergarten" OR "preschool" OR "nursery") AND ("systematic review" OR review OR "best evidence" OR "meta-analysis" OR "literature review") AND ("assessment strategies" OR "assessment practice")

(assessment OR evaluation OR assessing) AND ("early years" OR "early childhood education" OR "kindergarten" OR "preschool" OR "nursery") AND ("systematic review" OR review OR "best evidence" OR "meta-analysis" OR "literature review") AND (learning OR develop OR agency OR participation OR dispositions)

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Accessible in English
- Published in any country
- Published in a peer reviewed academic journal
- Refers to assessment with children 0-5
- Refers to assessment in numeracy, literacy, or digital literacy
- Refers to assessment of learning, curriculum, practice, environment or setting
- Refers to assessment practices or strategies
- Refers to different types of assessment

Exclusion criteria

- Published prior to 2011
- Published in a non peer reviewed academic journal
- Refers to assessment in primary years
- Refers to neurological, psychological or health screening or assessment

- Refers to children with special needs
- Refers to evaluation of programmes or interventions

Note: Due to the holistic nature of early childhood education studies referring to assessment practices and strategies that did not exclusively refer to literacy or numeracy were not excluded.

Key Data Sources Consulted

Databases consulted

- Academic Search Complete
- British Education Index
- Education Research Complete
- EBSCO
- ERIC International
- Google Scholar
- IDESR
- SCOPUS

Other sources consulted

- Handbooks in the field published since 2011
- 'Grey literature' (reports published by international and national organisations/governments)

Figure 1. PRISMA flow chart

Source: extracted from Covidence software on 18/08/21

Review (Authors)	Purpose	#	Age range	Period of time covered	Key Findings
Alaçam 2021	Identify what we know about practices of pedagogical documentation in early childhood education	24	Preschool age	2006-2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedagogical documentation is an alternative form of assessment • Documenting: (1) contributes to children’s learning, teachers’ awareness of learning processes, and parents’ gaining a better understanding of their children’s learning processes (Buldu, 2010); (2) provides a significant record of teaching and learning for each stakeholder (MacDonald, 2007); (3) makes children’s perspectives visible and open for reflection; (4) enables children to be able to remember more factual information in documentation and worksheet (Fleck et al., 2013); (5) promotes literacy by providing deeper understanding of children’s interest, curiosity and strength while presenting literacy activities (Mac Donald, 2007). (p.176); (6) show children’s metacognitive and self-regulatory skills, and it improves the quality of discussion between teachers and children (Aras & Tantekin Erden, 2019). • In documentations, it was mostly the children’s achievements that were visible. This has been criticized as causing the risk of evaluating child through achievements, rather than their individual

					<p>performance or who they are (Emilson & Samuelsson, 2014).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall, pedagogical documentation has desired outcomes for children, parents, and teachers but this depends on the effectiveness of teachers' fulfilling their roles in the process.
Brunsek 2017	Evaluate the association between ECERS and children's wellbeing	73	Preschool age	Up to July 2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECERS captures aspects of the learning environment that are important to child development but there are substantial limitations of research on its use. Some evidence to support a positive but weak relationship between ECERS and child outcomes.
Buckingham 2014	Outline the research evidence on the main factors that interact with, or mediate, the influence socio-economic disadvantage exerts on literacy ability and achievement in the years prior to and the first few years of school	Not specified	Preschool + school age	2000-2014	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental factors are the most important factors in determining children's reading development. • Poor phonological awareness is characteristic of most poor readers, sometimes compounded by other language deficits such as low vocabulary • Teaching and assessment practices need to consider this reality.
Cloney 2019	Provide a comprehensive resource that will equip early childhood professionals with the knowledge to identify and assess children's progress towards children as confident and involved learners.	Not specified	0-8	Not specified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In assessing children as confident and involved learners, educators face questions about how to select appropriate measures across phases of development, how to administer assessments, how to interpret the results, and how to translate their findings into planning and communication to parents. The following six principles for assessing learning have been identified in this review, and these can inform early childhood professional practice: (1) Assessment addresses established

					<p>components of children’s learning; (2) Assessment enables early childhood professionals to describe a continuum of learning; (3) Assessment is valid, reliable and fair; (4) Assessment is conducted in a way that enhances engagement and relationships; (5) Assessment includes children’s self-assessment; (6) Assessment involves the child’s community and informs professional partnerships.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The review identifies the following assessment tools: Dimensional Change Card Sort (DCCS); Measuring Early Learning Quality and Outcomes (MELQO); Measure of Development and Early Learning (MODEL); Measuring Early Learning Quality and Outcomes (MELQO); Ages & Stages Questionnaires, Third Edition (ASQ-3); Social Skills Improvement System (SSIS); Early Abilities Based Learning and Education Support (Early ABLES); Who Am I? (WAI); Children’s Independent Learning Development 3–5 (CHILD 3–5); Leuven Involvement Scale for Young Children (LIS-YC); Preschool Learning Behaviors Scale (PLBS); Individualized Classroom Assessment Scoring System (inCLASS)
Correia 2019	Systematically address literature on children's participation in ECE	36	0-5	1980-2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refers to the importance of children's participation in their own learning, which includes an active role in their own assessment.
Hussain 2019	Examine the usefulness of Dynamic Assessment for practitioners in ECE	5	0-5	Not specified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are several limitations to standardised assessment, which imposes restrictions on practice, limits understanding of children and fails to engage with the wider social context of the child.

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic assessment may be used as an alternative assessment to extend or replace standardised assessment. This approach enables us to work collaboratively and discover what works for young children. • There is a need for alternative modes of assessment to enhance the data already being collected.
Jackson 2020	Provide a comprehensive resource that will equip early childhood professionals with the knowledge to identify and assess children's progress towards children's strong sense of identity	Not specified	0-8	Not specified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principles to choose an assessment strategy: (1) Relevance of construct; (2) Usefulness for educators; (3) Validity, reliability and fairness • Principles that should guide assessment: (1) Assessment addresses established components of children's identity; (2) Assessment enables early childhood professionals to describe a trajectory of identity development; (3) Assessment is valid, reliable and fair; (4) Assessment is conducted in a way that enhances engagement and relationships; (5) Assessment includes children's self-assessment; (6) Assessment involves the child's community and informs professional partnerships. • Suggested assessment strategies: focused observation, learning stories, Ages and stages questionnaire, Strange situation and Berkeley, Puppet interview.
LouiseMarbina 2015	Provide a comprehensive resource that will equip early childhood professionals with the knowledge to identify and assess children's	Not specified	0-8	Not specified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principles of assessing (1) Effective assessment needs a clearly defined purpose; (2) Effective assessment is based on multiple sources of information; (3) Assessment includes individual, group and centre evidence; (4) Assessment

	progress towards children's wellbeing				includes children's own reports; (5) Assessment of wellbeing includes evidence from parents; (6) Assessment is an opportunity for multidisciplinary collaboration.
Noble 2020	Provide a comprehensive resource that will equip early childhood professionals with the knowledge to identify and assess children's progress towards children connected with and contribute to their world	Not specified	0-8	Not specified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are relatively few contemporary tools available to assess how children are connected and contribute to the world. • Principles for assessment: (1) Assessment addresses established components of children's connection with and contribution to their world; (2) Assessment enables early childhood professionals to describe a trajectory of development; (3) Assessment is valid, reliable and fair; (4) Assessment is conducted in a way that enhances engagement and relationships; (5) Assessment includes children's self-assessment; (6) Assessment involves the child's community and informs professional partnerships.
Perlman 2016	Evaluate associations between CLASS domain and dimension scores in classrooms that served preschool aged children and children's concurrent or subsequent social, emotional and cognitive outcomes.	35	Preschool age	until 2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLASS operationalises very difficult constructs but not all of them are linked to child outcomes. Although it captures important aspects of ECE services, from the available literature it is not possible to conclude that there is a link to quality or to child outcomes.
Soto 2019	Carry out a systematic review of current phonological awareness interventions by evaluating the quality and efficacy of studies	15	Preschool age	2000-2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This study provides an evaluation of the quality and effects of phonological awareness interventions.

	based on their design characteristics and intervention effects.				
Teale 2020	Examine patterns found in early literacy research appearing in English-language publications during the period from 2006 through 2015.	6948	Preschool age	2006-2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Four patterns or trends discerned through the literature: (1) Accretion; (2) Influence of 'scientifically valid' research; (3) Limited response to increasingly diverse student populations; (4) Increased research focus on younger children • Through the systematic review there was a focus on assessment (6% of the sample studies). However, these studies 'were primarily concerned with assessing the validity and or reliability of developed measures' (p.200). • Invernizzi et al. (2010) cautioned against the overuse of preschool assessments in the US.(p.200).

Table 1. Systematic reviews consulted

Source: elaborated by the authors based on Covidence extraction on 18/08/21

Consulted text (Authors)	Purpose	Relevance to this chapter
Alasuutari 2014	Explore how children are assessed and documented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment is 'a culturally contradictory issue in Nordic ECE' (p.3) • Documentation is a cultural choice and practice • Documentation positions the educator, child, parents • In early childhood assessment, the 'norms of the white middle-class usually predominate (e.g. Hosp & Reschly, 2004; Lappalainen, 2004). • Multi-documentation in ECEC produces a documentalized childhood (the child is defined and produced in and by documentation. • Challenge of time in generating and enacting documentation
Auld 2019	Analyse the dynamics of the IELTS project in the context of comparative testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There's an attempt to introduce a new paradigm for early childhood education based on: (a) a universal standard of education quality; (b) a cognitive-economic model of education, supplemented with a focus on non-cognitive dimensions such as well-being, global competence and social and emotional skills; (c) alignment of national and/or regional level assessments with a global standard; (d) a global policy network, and transfer of 'best practice'; (5) increased private sector involvement in each stage of the process (i.e.measurement, analysis, reform); (6) (for 'developing' nations) incentivised compliance and punitive accountability (Auld et al., 2018)
Basford 2014	Describe the recent statutory guidance about assessment and documentation for English ECE settings and deconstructs the latest English ECE policies, high-lighting that these often give contradictory messages to practitioners.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The paper suggests that practitioners are caught up in playing a game: trying to make compatible assessment practices that address both the scientific discourse of empiricism and a more recent internationally influenced sociocultural discourse. • Two competing assessment paradigms: a positivist approach (individualistic, developmental, decontextualised) vs a sociocultural (social, cultural and localised)

Bradbury 2011	Deconstruct the relationship between assessment results and inequality.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The article questions the assumption that results only record inequality, rather than being implicated in its production. It argues the English system creates incentives for educators to keep the scores of marginalised children low.
Buzzelli 2018	Conceptualise assessment in ECE as a moral practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment as a moral practice must be done from two perspectives: from the learner’s perspective to assess children’s agency in guiding their own learning, and from the environment’s perspective to assess the opportunities for learning afforded children by the environment. Balancing assessment from these two perspectives is a moral challenge for teachers. • Addressing the dual perspectives on assessment has presented challenges to conducting capability approach research with children. From one point of view, assessments should address what children are able to do and be from the children’s perspectives. From the other, there is a necessity for respecting the legal and moral responsibilities of the adults who care for young children. For teachers, this means balancing children’s agency and freedom against their responsibility as teachers for guiding children’s learning and development. This balance poses theoretical, moral, and practical challenges
Cameroon 2018	Clarify the different notions of assessment in ECE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment as learning is not that well understood in ECE
Casberg 2011	Understand the relationship between literacy and assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key points: (1) How we understand literacy determines/ influences assessment – developmental, readiness, constructivist; (2) Testing versus assessment; (3) Negative consequences of testing in early childhood • Many of the problems associated with traditional assessments can be overcome through the use of documentary, or observational, assessment. • Situated assessment—that which occurs in the context of activities and contexts that are familiar to children. • Teachers who have gathered carefully collected and well-documented assessment information in addition to scores from traditional tests are especially

		well positioned to support all aspects of children’s development and learning—and to begin to change perceptions about what counts and what should be counted in early childhood education.
Conti-Ramsden 2012	Norm-referenced instruments for assessing language abilities in preschool children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of language abilities in preschool should involve evaluation of both expressive and receptive skills (more than one dimension of language). • The use of a single measure of a language component, such as vocabulary, is considered inadequate.
Cooper 2014	Teacher’s view on involving families in assessment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance in this model of teacher/educator observation as a means of assessment • These findings highlight the complexities of implementing TeWhariki’s sociocultural principle of involving families in assessment through two-way partnerships, in a setting guided by RIE and its underlying developmental perspectives.
DeLuca 2019	Explore how kindergarten teachers leverage assessment practices, particularly Assessment as Learning (AaL) to support children learning within play-based classrooms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous assessment in Kindergarten + Assessment for learning and Assessment as learning. • Pedagogical documentation can be a useful assessment for learning • Developmental assessment approach (developmental checklists and observations) • Blended approach to assessment – differentiation of curricula and a balance between social and academic development (baseline data/formative and summative assessments) • Assessment for learning – ensuring students were meeting curriculum standards while maintaining a developmental approach • Where assessment was developmental/academic in nature the specific focus was on Literacy /Numeracy • Teachers are concerned with the abundance of data and inability to make meaning from it.

DeLuca 2020	How assessment in kindergarten education can promote children’s self-regulation and independence for early school success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A focus on AaL and self-regulation might be the fulcrum that hinges play-pedagogies with standards-based education and assessment mandates. • Many different types of assessment—both standards-based and developmentally oriented—are required to properly understand children’s learning, share that understanding with them and support the growth of self-regulated learning.
Ebbeck 2014	Report on curriculum effectiveness using developmental learning outcomes as a means of assessing children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment is important to help children learn, communicate with families and for accountability reasons. It is important this assessment is purposeful and developmentally appropriate. • Purposeful assessment provides the early childhood educator with: (1) Objective information from the everyday activities occurring in a centre and from multiple sources that allow a representative view of children’s developmental profiles and progress in learning outcomes. This information allows for professional discussions and the valid interpretation of information that can present a holistic view of each child’s development; (2) Information about the overall learning effectiveness of the curriculum which allow gaps in the curriculum content to be identified; (3) Information about the extent to which planned developmental learning outcomes are being achieved by children and the flagging of any needed redirection; (4) Information to vary children’s developmental profile if needed; (5) Identification of children who are at risk and who need to be referred for specialist assistance; (6) Shared perspectives from teaching staff and parents of children’s current and future development. Assessment strategies; (7) Direct, focused observation and recording to find out about children’s naturally occurring behaviour during their routines, play, curriculum activities, and in their interactions with their teachers and peers; (8) Through analysis of anecdotal records taken over time including analysis of children’s play episodes, and how their friendships develop and change. Such anecdotes allow teachers to reflect and discuss with parents how children are growing and developing.
Formosinho 2017	Critically explore the nature, purposes and value of assessment and evaluation processes within a participatory pedagogy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment and evaluation processes are required which match a complex democratic, dynamic and multi-dimensional educational reality.

Fundus 2015	Determine whether ECERS reflects children's progress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students made progress whether their classroom passed the ECERS-R requirement or did not. Therefore, the ongoing question for many educators is whether the ECERS-R is a worthwhile measure of quality within preschool programs (Cryer et al., 2005). The ECERS-R tool has been used in many preschool programs since the 1980s and has provided a great guide for program improvement. However, when using this measure to evaluate quality, school district personnel must carefully consider the meaning and importance of low scores, because some subsections, such as handwashing, do not relate to quality instruction impacting student achievement.
Hoffman 2014	Review the forms of vocabulary assessment commonly used with young children, examining the benefits and drawbacks of each	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vocabulary is a critical factor in literacy development, both during early childhood (National Early Literacy Panel (NELP, 2008) and throughout schooling (Baumann, 2008). • There are several unexplored problems with the ways in which young children's vocabulary learning is assessed. • Assessments used in the field fell into two main categories: measures of general vocabulary or knowledge of specific words, either of which may assess the depth or breadth of word knowledge.
Johnson 2019	Investigation of young children's counting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment processes are not sufficiently sophisticated to capture the complexity of children's thinking • Skills such as counting do not develop in isolated fashion (so why would you try to assess discrete aspects of Mathematics) • Not about content knowledge specifically but about children's emergent understanding of the patterns and structure of the number sequence as they attempt to extend their sequence
McKie 2012	Examine the Pre-Kindergarten Incentive Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This study focuses on kindergarten readiness. Focuses on assessment environment/practices rather than individual children: The Early Language and Literacy Classroom Observation (ELLCO) and the Early Childhood Environment Rating Scale-Revised Edition (ECERS-R).

Ntuli 2014	Explore early childhood teachers' perceptions of assessment measures used with immigrant children and the challenges faced when assessing immigrant children.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early childhood teachers fail to gather effective assessment information from immigrant children. • Teacher challenges: Language barriers, Culturally and linguistically unresponsive assessment measures, Lack of parent's full participation in the assessment process, Lack of knowledge of early childhood development, Cultural clashes
Picchio 2014	Explore the use of documentation in a participatory system of evaluation, which is used in Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PD is not used to assess children but assess practice and provision • PD to document children's experiences and parents experiences
Raghubar 2017	Review the emerging literature on the acquisition of early numeracy skills and briefly consider implications for early assessment and intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The association between early numeracy skills and formal mathematics learning warrants assessment of early numeracy skills. • Advocates for the instruction of mathematical concepts and procedures in preschool.
Roberts-Holmes 2019	Examine why the government in England has signed the country up to take part in this new international assessment; highlight the role of IELTS as a technology of neoliberal governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What both IELTS and Baseline Assessment also exemplify is the central role for data and statistics in neoliberal governing, what has been termed 'datafication' and 'dataveillance', that is the collection and analysis of data on children to ensure compliance to prescribed standards and targets (Bradbury and Roberts-Holmes, 2017). Comparative educational data, whether the comparison is between schools in the same country or between schools in different countries, has become an important way to govern teachers, schools and nations as 'a neoliberal logic of control fits neatly with the ways that individuals are "made up" by data' (Lyon, 2014). This 'tyranny of numbers' (Ball, 2015) describes the increasing importance of data in the every-day lives of those working in the education of young children (Bradbury and Roberts-Holmes, 2017). • IELTS forms part of expanding and increasingly dense webs of standardised educational measurement, webs that are both national, spun for instance by the UK government, and international, spun under the aegis of OECD. In both cases, national and international, these webs of standardised assessment of performance are an integral part of neoliberal governing, applying measures of

		performance as the basis for managing diverse situations – a market of competing schools in England; a market of competing countries globally.
Roberts-Holmes 2017	Policy analysis of baseline assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early years baseline assessment was designed to produce a ‘baseline’ data figure on the basis of which young children’s progress across the primary years could be digi-tally measured, and was to form a key part of how schools were to be held to account in the future. Baseline assessment proved to be a highly controversial policy initiative, as the accountability measure is conducted with 4-year-old children in their first few weeks of formal schooling. Baseline resulted in a single digital data score for each child: when they reached year 6, and were 11 years old, each child in the cohort would have been measured against their reception baseline score, from age 4, in order to judge the progress they had made while attending primary school. Baseline, therefore, represented a further shift towards the datafication of accountability in primary education, which involved the early years phase more than ever before • Baseline’s reductionism facilitates comparison through its potential to hierarchically rank children, schools and local authorities.
Scul 2021	Design and validation of a new instrument 'the Early Literacy engagement Assessment (ELEA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment in ECEC involves observing, recording and documenting children's learning; to observe and record sensitively, there is a need for well-informed assessment tools and analysis frame; conversational reading underpins the tool (ELEA). • The ELEA is compared with Conversational Reading (another assessment tool). • However, no one technique is sufficiently reliable on its own, and assessment methods have been widely critiqued (Grolig, 2020). As such, educators need to make informed decisions as they assess young learners, taking into account the social dimensions of language and literacy to be assessed, the selection of assessment tools and the way these data are used to inform teaching and support students’ learning (Johnston & Costello, 2005) (p.190)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This shifts the emphasis from isolated tests of language and school readiness devoid of context to tools that draw on familiar-authentic classroom practices (Clay, 2019)
Verdon 2017	Identify and review a range of assessment tools that early childhood professionals can use to assess how effectively children use communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observation identifies the need for assessment (communication) • Some elements of communication that can be assessed: Speech – production and perception of speech sounds and syllables (for example, articulation, phonology); language – expressive and receptive vocabulary, grammar, sentence structure, narrative, discourse; voice – vocal quality; fluency – stuttering; pragmatics – social communication; literacies – mark-making, scribbling, drawing, writing, spelling, reading, engagement with multimedia; hearing, vision, cognition, fine and gross motor skills.
Yoon 2015	Analyse standardised literacy assessment. Illustrate the partial picture that basic skills mastery paints of children’s language competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discourses of readiness and achievement gaps mask issues of race and inequality. "Readiness demands that children grasp a defined skills set, deemed rigorous, with timely developmental progressions. • Assessment practices created a separation and grouping of children according to ability levels. • Assessment scripts cannot capture the complete story of children abilities. Not captured by time constraints and measurable tests; " complex ways that children practise literacy.""
Zhang 2017	Uncover educator and parental responses to learning stories as a tool of assessing children's learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voice/perspective of the child is not included • Challenge the notion of parental involvement • Inability of Learning Stories to capture 'milestones' • Query if Learning Stories are individual or team affairs

Table 2. Other sources consulted

Source: elaborated by the authors based on Covidence extraction on 18/08/21